
Behavioral intervention design for scaling innovative services promoting smart sustainability

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Abstract: This research addresses the question of how to overcome the innovation chasm in the field of new smart city services, which enable living a sustainable lifestyle. The gap between smart city visionaries (early adopters) and pragmatist users (early majority) is a particular challenge in the innovation scaling phase here, because also the free use of sustainability services is very often associated with the change of behavioral routines (e.g. bike-use instead of car-use). To meet the challenge of scaling innovative smart city services, we suggest investigating the suitability of behavioral economic concepts of incentives, nudges, gamified challenges and rewards. Further, we aim to explore the preferences for specific target-group-oriented incentive approaches in the field of bicycle mobility. Based on the first results (literature review, survey) we will propose a specific intervention design for nudging sustainability services that will be then tested and evaluated in two European smart cities (JPI-Urban Europe: www.simplicity-project.eu).

Keywords: Innovation diffusion theory, innovation nudge, behavioral economic concepts, digital services for a sustainable city lifestyle

1 Problem

In order to manage the increasing number of citizens, governments around the world have already launched multiple smart city (SC) initiatives focusing on the development of new IoT (Internet of Things) applications, wireless networks or web- and mobile-based applications. These technologies enable citizens to live a more sustainable life, which aims at producing less carbon emission, using more energy efficient services and supporting local consumption and a more inclusive lifestyle (Harter et al, 2010; Cohen, 2017). Smart city services include analogue and digital offers and cover a wide variety of application areas such as mobility, energy, social services, governability/ public services or waste management. However, until now these innovative IT solutions and services have become only successful with smart city visionaries and lead-users and are failing to reach the early majority of not so technology savvy or less enthusiastic citizens. The problem is that many of SC services which are regarded as "hybrid services", serving both individual customer needs and common goods, are not linked to initiatives focusing on raising people's awareness, or promoting and rewarding the necessary individual behavioral change (Kazhamiakin et al., 2016). In other words, the "tragedy of the commons" applies, because citizens act in their own interest and not by considering the overall goal and needs of "their city" for a more sustainable lifestyle.

The research contribution addresses the question of how to overcome the innovation chasm in the field of new smart city services, which promote and enable living a sustainable lifestyle. The gap between smart city visionaries (early adopters) and pragmatist users (early majority) is a particular challenge in the innovation scaling phase here, because also the free use of sustainability services is very often associated with the change of behavioral routines. For example, the use of a digital Smart Mobility Routing app that suggests taking the bicycle instead of using the car for the benefit of a CO₂-limited city only works well if the user is fully motivated to change their mobility behavior. To meet the challenge of scaling innovative smart city services, we suggest investigating the suitability of behavioral economic concepts of incentives, nudges and rewards etc. Further, we aim to explore the core motives and preferences for specific target-group-oriented incentive approaches in the field of bicycle mobility. Based on the first results (literature review, survey) we will propose a specific intervention design for nudging sustainability services that will be then tested and evaluated in two European smart cities (JPI-Urban Europe: www.simplicity-project.eu).

2 Current understanding

The problems mentioned above require innovative solutions, otherwise public smart city managers miss the mark. User-centric design and behavioral economics insights are seen as powerful solution to overcome the lack of users and close the gap between early adopters and the early majority. Insights especially from nudging, as one strand in behavioral economics (Thaler & Sunstein, 2009), have established itself across various sectors in governance and policy instrumentation. However, there is only limited systematic analysis of how to use nudging in the field of smart urban sustainability (Esmark, 2017). While there are already many guidelines for implementing nudges in offline environments (e.g. placing healthy food at eye level in supermarkets), digital nudging has only recently become the focus of interest for digital user interface designers (Schneider et al., 2018). Scientific results and evaluated success stories are still limited. Methods from behavioral economics (e.g. monetary-/ non-monetary incentives, nudges, reward mechanisms, challenges) have already been tested in the field of health-related issues (Vallgård, 2012; Marteau, 2011), but findings regarding sustainability related objectives are still limited.

As is known from the growing bulk of literature in behavioral economics and social psychology, motivational incentives play an important role in influencing people's decision-making and thus their behavior. According to Lu et al. (2018: 3438) and based on the Oxford Standard dictionary, an incentive is *a thing that motivates or encourages someone to do something* and can be divided either in monetary or non-monetary incentives. Monetary or financial incentives are payments made to encourage desired change, however there are different types of rewards besides direct payments. Financial incentives, same as non-financial incentives can either be positive (rewards) or negative (penalties) (Hall, 2009). In the scientific literature monetary incentives are especially present in the fields of health and employee motivation, but some best practice examples (such as the initiative "Kilometric cycling allowance" in France, 2017, <http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/cycling-kilometric-allowance-france>) show that monetary incentives are a suitable method for motivating people to change their mobility behavior and decision-making for another mean of transport for commuting.

Non-monetary incentives, on the other hand, do not involve any direct payment and can either be tangible or intangible. In the context of incentivisation towards a certain behavior, non-monetary incentives are often found in reward systems, such as in the non-profit initiative "goodbag" (<https://www.goodbag.io/>). This approach aims to engage people in environmental protection by using different incentives

such as vouchers or rebates for local shops if they use a reusable shopping bag equipped with an NFC chip instead of a plastic one. Another way of motivating people in a non-monetary way are regulations, which are, according to Ly & Soman (2013: 6) defined as *restrictions, bans, compliance rules, and similar forms of regulation impose behavioural limitations that individuals or corporations are expected to comply with*, or information which ensures that people make better informed decisions. Information and education programmes are often used, for example, in personal health and savings programmes to improve learning and individual knowledge.

In recent years, there is a growing interest in the concept of nudging, that is based on insights from behavioural economics, which describes how behavioural changes are triggered by gentle incentives. Nudges are used to influence people's behaviour without resorting to other methods such as commandments or prohibitions or economic incentive systems (Ly & Soman, 2013). Basically, the concept describes how people can be steered in particular directions such as avoiding unhealthy food, without taking them the possibility to go their own way. In other terms, nudges influence behaviour by changing the way decisions are made, instead of imposing restrictions or economic incentives. Various authors, such as Sunstein, 2014; Thorun et al., 2016; Mont et al., 2014, provide an overview about the most effective types of nudging, whereas the University College London developed a comprehensive *taxonomy on behaviour change techniques (BCT)* that has been hierarchically clustered and defined (Michie et al, 2013).

As different nudges are required for different targets and within different contexts, a structured process as proposed by Ly et al. is required. Therefore, it is essential to design an effective nudging strategy in the first place. An analysis of the context and the task is required to identify how people make decisions or what are the usual behavioural habits in typical circumstances. Then the key heuristics and influences that may affect the decision outcome need to be identified (Ly et al., 2013).

Figure 1: Nudging process (Source: Ly et al, 2013)

3 Research questions

Since there is only limited knowledge on how to design intervention campaigns in the field of smart city initiative relying on insights from behavioral economics (nudging and incentivisation) and about choosing suitable nudging or incentivisation tools for specific target groups, the research focusses on the following questions:

- What are the success factors and enablers of digital behavior-based interventions for smart city services?
- Which methods and tools are appropriate to incentivize people and are appropriate to change people's behavior by the use of ICT?
- Under which conditions is it necessary to address specific target groups in cities (young, elderly, women, men, etc.) with different methods and incentive (gamified) approaches?

4 Research design

The research questions will be tackled within a major research project funded from the Joint Programming Initiative Urban Europe – Making cities work, which focusses on digital services and incentive design for smart sustainable communities and incentive design for smart sustainable communities SimpliCITY" (2018-2020, www.simplicity-project.eu). Firstly, this project explores the methods and tools for behavioral design and incentivisation methods as well as best practices cases for (incentivizing) smart city bike services. Secondly, it identifies user preferences for different intervention instruments and based on that, thirdly, develops an intervention design to be tested and evaluated in two pilot demonstrations in two European cities, Uppsala (SWE) and Salzburg (AUT). The used behavioral intervention actions are terminated and scientifically evaluated as to the nudging effects. Altogether, the project delivers the instruments to raise the awareness and promote changes towards a sustainable city lifestyle by testing and evaluating these methods and tools.

5 Findings

The main output of the research will be an empirically sound base on insights from behavioral economics, focusing on methods and tools on how to incentivize people

in order to use the new smart city services for the common good of our cities. The preliminary results show which methods and tools are suitable for specific target groups and thematic areas and can be recommended to smart city managers for scaling.

Based on the results of the literature research, 15 international good practice cases and expert interviews in our thematic areas (bicycle mobility, local consumption and production as well as social integration), the first essential conclusions can be drawn:

- The overall effectiveness of an intervention for Smart City services increases if, for example, game or social norm actions are combined with upstream information actions.
- Additionally, the use of different forms of applications (like navigation apps in the mobility area) plays an important role in this process.

Further preliminary findings are based on a survey, conducted at a local bike event in Salzburg, AT (Radfrühling, May 2019). By means of this survey, 125 people reported on their mobility behavior and their everyday mobility. Specifically, they were asked about what would motivate them to bike more or to use selected bike services, offered by the city, more often. The questions were split up in mobility behavior in everyday life and in leisure time. For the evaluation of the data, special attention was paid on characteristics within different age groups.

First findings show that physical changes of the environment motivate people most to bike more often (58,06%), followed by the availability of information (38,71%). Incentives such as vouchers are the third-best way people feel motivated to bike more (30,65%). Playful elements are rated the lowest, as people tend to have a more pragmatically approach for their daily distances (Challenges, 20,97%; Gamification, 15,32%). Whereas, first results show that, even though the infrastructure is still the most influencing factor, people are more interested in playful elements within their leisure time. In this case 23,39% of the interviewed people would be motivated to bike more when challenges are offered and 21,77% would bike more when offering gamification interventions.

When focusing on the actual target group of the study, people who do not yet cycle on a regular basis, no significant differences of the individual preference toward a specific type of motivation can be identified. However, people who do not, or not on a regular basis bike, are slightly more motivated by incentives such as vouchers or discounts for biking more often, than already cycling citizens (this group summarizes people who stated that they use their bike on a daily basis, several times a week or at least once a week). Non-cycling citizens would also be motivated to bike more often by being provided more information on bike services or biking infrastructure.

Figure 2: Incentive preference by mobility behaviour – Daily biking

Figure 3: Incentives preference by mobility behaviour (biking vs. non-biking citizens) - Leisure time

In addition, the results show that playful elements such as games or challenges tend to motivate younger target groups between 19 and 40 years of age. Figures 4 and 5 show how many people in the specific target groups would be motivated to drive more given specific methods and tools. No significant difference between everyday life and leisure time mobility has been observed.

In order to obtain a broader and more representative sample, this survey continues and is also aimed at non-cyclists, as 53% of those surveyed who do not cycle or only rarely cycle indicated that they could imagine using their bicycle daily when cycling becomes more attractive for them.

Figure 4: Playful elements - Everyday Life - Age groups

Figure 5: Playful elements – Leisure time - Age groups

6 Contributions

Much research has already been done in the field of incentivisation and nudging dealing with health-related issues (see Esmark, 2017; Thaler & Sunstein, 2009) whereas research on the potential of nudging for sustainable services/ lifestyle is limited, even though it is expected to have a positive influence (Lehner, 2016). A few examples in the field of influencing energy consumption by nudging initiatives already provide orientation, whereas the knowledge about long-term behavioral change towards a more sustainable lifestyle through digital tools and methods for incentivizing people is still limited. This research aims not only at discussing the relevance of theoretical behavioral economics insights for innovation management research, but also at delivering practical findings (pilot demonstration of scientific framework). We will use our experience and methods to tackle the challenge of innovation scaling and designing effective intervention campaigns to achieve better decisions and more commitment by smart citizens and reaching common sustainability goals.

7 Practical implications

The expected results of the research will on the one hand provide a sound basis for smart city managers, often acting as public innovation managers. Innovation researchers will be able to connect insights from behavioral economics in overcoming the chasm in the innovation cycle. Target group specific knowledge about incentivisation methods and tools will support innovation and smart city managers by designing interventions to overcome the intention-action gap in the early phase of public service innovations.

8 Research issues to be discussed (Feedback questions)

- 1) On the research approach (experiences of similar research)?
- 2) How can other innovation research and managers (e.g. smart city management) as well as service providers benefit more from insights from behavioral economics and nudging in their daily work?

- 3) Are any other researchers interested in cooperation about empirical research on how to assess influence of methods and digital tools from behavioral economics for sustainable development? Are any cities interested in joining the pilot demonstrations?
- 4) What influence do cultural differences within Europe have on the effectiveness of nudging? Are studies available that deal with this topic?

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